

Deuterium-Hydroxyl Exchange over Supported Metal Catalysts

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The exchange between hydrogen adsorbed on platinum and supported hydroxyl groups has been studied by a temperature-programmed exchange technique. It was found that platinum shifted the deuterium-hydroxyl exchange to temperatures below those observed for pure γ -alumina or silica. The method by which the catalyst was prepared had a marked effect on the exchange and on the density of hydroxyl groups on the support. In general, it was found that impregnation with H_2PtCl_6 increased the hydroxyl concentration in contrast to impregnation with $Pt(NH_3)_4(NO_3)_2$. In order to assess the importance of the metal-support interface in promoting hydrogen atom spillover, the adsorption of hydrogen atoms generated in the gas phase to a variety of oxide supports, reported to be active in promoting hydrogen atom spillover, was studied. It was concluded that hydrogen atom adsorption was insufficient to account for catalytic enhancement due to hydrogen atom migration across the support. In the light of our data, it seems likely that catalytic enhancement due to support-adsorbate interactions are limited to the metal support interface.

WHEN considering the activity of supported metal catalysts, it is necessary to take into account reactions which take place at the metal-support interface and on the support in addition to those which take place solely on the surface of the metal. Reactions taking place at the metal interface and on the support have not received the attention that they deserve. In fact, studies involving the possibility of activation at the metal, followed by migration to the support and subsequent reaction, have only recently been considered. In particular, if one of the reactants is adsorbed on the support and another is generated on the metal, it might be possible that an enhancement in catalytic activity might be observed due to reaction on the support, provided of course that there is a mechanism by which the transfer from the metal to the support can be made. This possibility has received considerable attention in the recent literature¹⁻¹², particularly in connection with hydrogenation reactions. It has been argued that hydrogen activation occurs on the metal followed by hydrogen atom migration to the support. This phenomenon has been termed hydrogen atom spillover. Those studies have not been without controversy; for example, Sinfelt and Lucchesi³ proposed such an explanation to account for enhanced catalytic activity in the hydrogenation of ethylene over platinum supported on alumina, however, Schlatter and Boudart⁸ discounted these results in the light of additional data showing that hydrocarbon contamination might account for this apparent enhancement in catalytic activity. When

the catalyst was exposed to air for short periods of time, these authors found that rates of ethylene hydrogenation over supported platinum were similar to rates on unsupported platinum. At present, advocates and opponents of hydrogen atom spillover seem to be about equally divided.

Undoubtedly, hydrogen atom spillover can and does occur under certain conditions. Levy and Boudart⁴ have published a plausible mechanism for the platinum catalysed reduction at room temperature, the water solvating a proton at the platinum surface of the support where it was subsequently released at the reduction site. This agrees with the work of Ravi and Shepard⁶ who found an increase in the rate of deuterium-hydroxyl exchange over supported iridium in the presence of certain adsorbed alcohols and aldehydes.

In the more recent literature, one cannot help but reflect on the work of Gardes *et al.*⁷, a very dramatic case of hydrogen atom spillover. In this work, nickel alumina catalyst was contacted with alumina and then the nickel phase was removed after exposing to hydrogen at 300° and the alumina was exposed to ethylene at room temperature. Extensive hydrogenation occurred implying that the spilled-over hydrogen was chemisorbed on the alumina support and subsequently reacted with ethylene, requiring no co-catalyst. Additional experiments by these workers¹² suggested extensive participation from the gas phase in this reaction. A similar report involving atom migration⁹ postu-

lated that hydrogen atoms were generated on iron impurities (2000 ppm) and then diffused to the support where they reacted with adsorbed ethylene, again requiring no co-catalyst for the transfer.

A central problem in understanding hydrogen atom spillover, is the mechanism by which a hydrogen atom can be transferred from the chemisorbed state on the metal to the support. The strength of the metal hydrogen bond must be at least equal to half the strength of a metal-hydrogen bond plus half the heat of adsorption. For a hydrogen atom adsorbed on platinum, this must be at least 60 kcal, a strong bond indeed. Thermal energies in excess of 800 K would normally be required to break such a bond if the adatom is to migrate across the support in the absence of a co-catalyst. This point of view, however, is perhaps an over simplification. Conceivably, one might have the transfer of a hydrogen atom from a strongly to a weakly adsorbed state on the metal followed by transfer to an energetic physisorbed state on the support. This might then revert to a more strongly bound chemisorbed state on the support. The mechanism would not then require the full 60 kcal, but considerably less energy, as shown schematically in Fig. 1. Another possibility might be that the electron from the chemisorbed hydrogen atom is

Fig. 1. Lennard Jones potential energy diagram for a plausible transfer mechanism from a metal surface to the support: (---) S, (—) M.

transferred to the d-band of the metal followed by proton migration. Although this seems more likely than hydrogen transfer, an additional problem arises that most supports are insulators. If protons are indeed the active migratory species, it would seem likely that the electron left behind on the metal should also migrate. Due to the insulating properties of most supports, it would then seem unlikely that the electron would ever get very far from the metal-support interface. This brings about another way in which catalytic activity can be enhanced. If one considers that a reactant can

be adsorbed on the support with a high degree of mobility, reactant molecules could diffuse to the metal interface and react. If the hydrogen concentration at the interface is high, one might conceivably get catalytic enhancement. The increase in catalytic activity resulting from this process should then depend on the interfacial surface area and be dispersion dependent. This appears to be the case for supported nickel. Taylor *et al.*^{1,2} found specific activities to be dependent on dispersion. However, no such dependence has been observed for catalytic hydrogenations over supported platinum.

In any proposed mechanism involving spillover followed by hydrogen atom migration, the thermodynamics of the overall process must be considered. For the Gibbs free energy of spillover to be negative, one must have an acceptor on the support capable of forming a bond with the adatom of comparable energy to that being broken on the metal. The entropy of spillover is of course positive, however, it is doubtful whether the TS_{sp} term is sufficiently large to overcome an endothermic H_{sp} at moderately low temperatures.

In the first part of this report, we have considered this particular aspect of the spillover problem. By generating hydrogen atoms in the gas phase, we have evaluated several supports reported to be active in promoting hydrogen atom spillover as to the existence of acceptor sites capable of adsorbing hydrogen atoms in the absence of a metal. In the second part of this study, we have considered the possibility of hydrogen enrichment at the metal-support interface by considering deuterium-hydroxyl exchange, *i.e.* enhanced exchange might provide indirect evidence for an enhancement in the catalytic activity due to an increase in the mobility of interfacial hydrogen.

Experimental

The reactor used to study the adsorption of hydrogen atoms is shown schematically in Fig. 2. It consisted of a 600 ml conical flask equipped with a tungsten filament silver soldered to vacuum tight leads. The filament could be heated electrically by means of a variac backed by a constant voltage transformer. In general, filament temperatures between 1600 and 2000 K as measured by an optical pyrometer, were found to yield a satisfactory hydrogen atom flux to perform the hydrogen adsorption studies. The hydrogen atoms produced at the hot filament, diffuse to the adsorbent which was spread over the bottom of the flask to form a layer roughly 0.2 cm thick. A simple kinetic theory calculation assuming a hydrogen pressure of 0.76 torr and complete equilibration at the filament, shows that the hydrogen atoms are well thermalised as they undergo an average of 10^5 collisions before reaching the surface. All these low pressures, gas phase recombinations are minimised so that a large fraction of the hydrogen atoms generated at the filament reach the surface. The reactor was

Fig. 2. Reactor and associated vacuum glassware.

connected to a conventional vacuum system capable of attaining an ultimate pressure of 1×10^{-6} torr. The adsorption could be followed by measuring the decrease in pressure using a McLeod gauge which was isolated from the reactor by a liquid nitrogen trap. This was found to be important as mercury contamination could lead to significant hydrogen adsorption. The reactor could be thermostated by immersing the entire flask in either liquid nitrogen or an ice-water-bath (273 K). Several experiments were performed at 373 K by using a boiling water-bath. In a typical adsorption experiment, an inlet of hydrogen consisting of approximately 4 moles yielding a total pressure of about 0.09 torr was taken. The filament was then turned on, and the pressure decrease was followed with the McLeod gauge. Surface area measurements were made using nitrogen adsorption at 77 K via the standard B.E.T. technique.

The deuterium-hydroxyl exchange experiments were performed using the rising temperature technique described by Hall and Lutinski¹⁴. In reviewing this technique, deuterium gas is circulated over the catalyst increasing its temperature linearly at a rate of 2° min^{-1} . The gas phase was monitored for hydrogen using a Dupont 104 mass spectrometer and the data was then displayed as percent hydrogen vs time. As each chemically different hydroxyl group exchange with deuterium at a different temperature, a series of superimposed sigmoid shaped curves appear on the graph.

A temperature programmed exchange chromatogram is obtained by plotting the time derivative from this curve against temperature, the area under each peak being roughly proportional to the number of hydroxyl groups of each chemically distinct type present on the surface. Since the exchange is first order, one can write,

$$V_s \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) = A(x_\infty - x) \rho^{-E_a/RT}$$

where, E_a is the apparent activation energy, dx/dt the rate of hydrogen appearance in the gas phase, x the concentration of hydrogen in the gas phase, and x_∞ the equilibrium value of x . Settling the second derivative equal to zero at the inflection point one has

$$E_a = \frac{RT_i^2 (dx/dt)_i}{(x_\infty - x)_i (dT/dt)_i}$$

where the subscript i indicates that the values for these variables must be taken at the inflection point. Implicit in these equations, is the neglect of an isotope effect and the assumption that no more than one chemically distinct hydroxyl group exchanges at any given temperature.

Even though this second assumption may seem somewhat questionable, nevertheless useful data may be obtained using this technique. The experimental details have been described elsewhere¹⁵.

Materials: Cab-O-Sil (Cabot, U.S.A.) is a high area silica material consisting of microspheres with little or no pore structure and is widely used as a support. Alon-c (Cabot) is the alumina analogue of Cab-O-Sil. It is reported to be about 90% alumina, main impurities being iron and nickel. The support referred to as Teichner's alumina was prepared following the reported procedure⁷ as closely as possible. The NaOAc treated alumina was prepared by refluxing γ -alumina (Alon-c) (18 g) with 1 M NaOAc (200 ml) for 26 h followed by filtering and washing with hot water. The slurry was then dried at 120° for 16 h. Tungsten trioxide was prepared according to the reported method⁹. Tungstic acid (Matheson, Coleman and Bell) was reagent grade. The cracking catalyst was a typical commercial Davison silica-alumina catalyst (W.R. Grace, U.S.A.) with a nominal 28% alumina, reported impurities being Fe (0.03%) and Na_2O (0.04%). The supported catalysts used in the deuterium-hydroxyl exchange experiments were prepared by impregnating either Cab-O-Sil or Alon-c with solutions of H_2PtCl_6 or $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Engelhardt, U.S.A.). The resulting slurry was air dried regularly during the drying process to retain uniformity. The dried catalysts were then ground and screened to a fine powder ($<100 \mu$) and stored for subsequent use. Those made from H_2PtCl_6 are denoted as C-catalysts and those prepared from $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ are denoted as A-catalyst.

Hydrogen gas was purified by passing it sequentially through deoxo unit, molecular sieve and a liquid nitrogen trap to remove oxygen and water. It was further purified by passing through a charcoal train at 77 K to remove trace amounts of oxygen. Deuterium (Matheson) was research grade with a reported deuterium enrichment of 98%. All gases were periodically checked for purity mass spectrometrically.

Catalyst pretreatment: Prior to each hydrogen atom adsorption experiment, the support under investigation was heated in flowing hydrogen for 12 h at 400°. In the deuterium-hydroxyl exchange

TABLE I—ADDITION OF HYDROGEN ATOMS TO VARIOUS SUPPORT OXIDES

Catalyst	B.E.T. Surface Area $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	No. of μ mol of gas					
		Adsorbed on surface at 77 K $\times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$	Coming off surface at room temp. $\times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$	Adsorbed on surface at 77 K $\times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$	Adsorbed on surface at 273 K $\times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$	Coming off surface after heating to 250 K and cooling to room temp. $\times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$	Adsorbed by surface at 273 K $\times 10^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$
Cab-O-Sil	581	0.67	0.08	0.64	1.13	0.06	1.12
Alon-c	96	0.96	0.07	0.91	1.97	0.29	1.68
Teichner's Al_2O_3	465	0.38	0.04	0.34	0.74	0.51	0.23
Al_2O_3 treated with NaOAc	415	0.22	0.03	0.19	0.23	0.13	0.10
Mechanical mixture of Cab-O-Sil and Alon-c	565	0.66	0.03	0.63	0.98	0.26	0.72
Tungsten trioxide*	30	Tr			42.5		

* Reaction not carried to completion.

experiments, samples (2.0 g) were charged to a quartz reactor and heated slowly to 500° where they were treated in flowing oxygen for 2 h. The catalyst was evacuated at 500° for 20 min and then reduced in flowing hydrogen for 3 h at the same temperature followed by evacuation for 12 h. The catalyst was cooled down to 100°, where the pressure was observed to be less than 1×10^{-6} torr. The catalysts prepared in this way were then ready for either exchange experiments or surface area determinations. Dispersions were calculated by hydrogen chemisorption measurements at 25°, the flat portion of the isotherm being extrapolated to zero pressure.

Results and Discussion

An increase in adsorption is indicated at 273 K over that at 77 K for all supports investigated as shown in Table 1. However, the total hydrogen adsorption (columns 2 and 5, Table 1) is significantly lower than that reported by Bianchi *et al.*¹³ (the total adsorption being $1.35 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ or $60 \mu \text{ mol g}^{-1}$, a difference of three- or four-orders). The measured BET surface area ($465 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) compares favourably with the value reported by Gardes *et al.*⁷ ($470 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The measured surface area for Alon-c treated with NaOAc was $415 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ as compared only to $96 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for Alon-c. Cab-O-Sil and Alon-c, though both showed relatively larger hydrogen adsorption than the other supports, a very small fraction (*i.e.* $< 1\%$) of this adsorbed hydrogen was desorbed by heating the reactor to 250° and cooling back to room temperature. Desorption of a significant fraction of hydrogen from the other supports could be due to the more catalytically active hydrogen than that adsorbed on Cab-O-Sil or Alon-c. The difficulty with which the hydrogen on these supports is removed implies a chemical reaction (*i.e.* rehydroxylation of siloxane bridges, for example) rather than adsorption.

In comparison to the hydrogen adsorption of these supports, tungsten trioxide showed a rapid reaction with hydrogen atoms to form an analogue of the tungsten bronzes. However, there is practically no uptake by tungsten trioxide at 77 K, whereas

at 273 K the reaction was very fast. This implies that the formation of the tungsten bronze is activated and would tend to corroborate the results of Boudart and Levy⁴, who showed that the slow step in the reduction was to the release of the solvated proton at the reduction site. Similar mechanisms can be invoked to explain the Pd-catalysed reduction of MoO_3 and Cr_2O_3 studied by Bond and Tripathi¹¹. The concept of a solvated proton as a possible migratory species is indeed an attractive one but certainly not essential as shown in this work.

Thus, it would seem unlikely that large concentrations of hydrogen atoms resulting from hydrogen atom spillover could cover insulating support such as those studied, however, these experiments do not preclude the occurrence of hydrogen atom spillover which can and possibly does occur in the presence of an appropriate hydrogen atom sink or at the metal-support interface. If hydrogen atoms generated in the gas phase are not significantly adsorbed on these supports, why should hydrogen atoms generated at a metal surface site behave so differently? This question is indeed an intriguing one which must be considered if this dilemma is to be solved. One possibility is that of metal support interactions leading to a possible interfacial enrichment of hydrogen beyond the metal support boundary. Reactant molecules diffusing across the support might also react with hydrogen at these boundaries leading to an enhanced catalytic activity. It can be assumed that hydrogen enrichment might occur in cases where there is a strong interaction between adsorbed hydrogen and the support. Certainly, a good indication of this interaction might be the activity for deuterium-hydroxyl exchange. The temperature programmed exchange chromatogram for deuterium-hydrogen exchange over both Cab-O-Sil and Alon-c is shown in Fig. 3. On silica, the exchange takes place at relatively high temperatures having only one chemically distinct hydroxyl group which exchanges at about 550°. For alumina, the situation appears to be more complex having at least three and possibly four chemically distinct hydroxyl groups which exchange

Fig. 3. Temperature programmed exchange chromatogram: (O) Cab-O-Sil and (Δ) Alon-o. Rate of temp. increase, 2° min^{-1} .

with deuterium agreeing with Hall and Lutonski¹⁴. Considering the model for γ -alumina proposed by Peri¹⁶, these chemically distinct hydroxyl groups could be taken to represent hydroxyl sites surrounded by either one, two, three or four oxide ions each having a different energy of activation for exchange.

When a silica supported nickel catalyst was subjected to the rising temperature exchange technique¹⁵, there was a significant change in the shape and the temperature at which the exchange took place. For a 2% nickel-silica catalyst, in addition to the high temperature exchange peak attributed to exchange on the support as in the case of pure Cab-O-Sil, a new broad peak centred at 280° appeared, which was dispersion-dependent and disappeared at concentrations of nickel in excess of 10%. Over this concentration range, average crystallite sizes as measured by hydrogen-deuterium exchange, increased from 19 \AA . This data suggest that in addition to a gas-support deuterium-hydrogen exchange having as a probable mechanism

there is also a metal assisted exchange, which takes place at lower temperatures with a lower activation energy. Conceivably, this exchange could take place according to the following mechanism.

The dependence of this exchange on dispersion supports this mechanism. Again, according to the decrease of the metal crystallite size the total

number of hydroxyl groups interacting with metal atoms must increase giving an enhanced low temperature exchange.

The effect of the metal is not as clear in the case of alumina supported platinum as in silica supported nickel. The temperature programmed exchange chromatogram is shown in Fig. 4 for different preparations. The C-catalysts have been prepared using H_2PtCl_6 and the A-catalysts by using $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ as impregnating salt. There is an

Fig. 4. Temperature programmed exchange chromatogram for alumina supported platinum: (O) 2% Pt-alumina (O) and (Δ) 2% Pt-alumina (A). Rate of temp. increase, 2° min^{-1} .

increase in the number of hydroxyl groups exchanging at 200° though the exchange temperatures appear to be very similar to those observed for plain alumina support. This increase in the low temperature exchange is more pronounced and the total hydroxyl concentration is increased in the case of the C-catalysts as compared to plain alumina; furthermore, the total hydroxyl concentration is decreased when the platinum amine salt is used in the preparation. An increase in the metal loading has practically no effect on the total hydroxyl concentration or on the temperature at which exchange occurs. This data is shown in Table 2. The increase in hydroxyl concentrations for the C-catalysts is explainable if one considers that HCl formed in the decomposition of H_2PtCl_6 reacts with the alumina surface to generate additional hydroxyl groups as,

TABLE 2—DEUTERIUM-HYDROXYL EXCHANGE OVER ALUMINA SUPPORTED PLATINUM

Catalyst	Dispersion H/Pt	Hydroxyl exchange temp., °C	Exchange energy of activation, kcal mol ⁻¹	OH cm ⁻³ × 10 ⁻¹⁴
Al ₂ O ₃ (Alon-c)	0.89	180, 260, 340, 480	1.1, 4.7, 13.0	1.50 ± 0.10
2% Pt-Al ₂ O ₃ (C)	0.89	200, 300, 440	4.4, 16.3, 33.9	
2% Pt-Al ₂ O ₃ (A)	0.91	220, 280, 430	4.3, 10.5, 32.6	1.30 ± 0.07
5% Pt-Al ₂ O ₃ (C)	0.65	200, 280, 440	4.4, 10.5, 33.0	1.88 ± 0.13
5% Pt-Al ₂ O ₃ (A)	0.64	200, 280, 430	4.4, 10.5, 32.6	1.35 ± 0.05

Fig. 5. Infrared spectra in the hydroxyl stretching region: (a) 1% Pt-alumina (A) and (b) 2% Pt-alumina (C).

These sites are similar to the so called sites described by Peri¹⁷ when HC reacts with the surface of γ -alumina. The difference in the concentration of hydroxyl groups between the C- and the A-catalysts should then be a measure of the HCl reaction. This difference is 3×10^{13} and 6×10^{13} hydroxyl cm⁻² for the 2% and 5% catalysts, respectively and compares with estimates of α -sites reported by Peri¹⁷. To substantiate these ideas further, we have recorded the infrared spectra in the hydroxyl stretching region for both the A- and the C-catalysts. These are shown in Fig. 5. The wider adsorption bands observed for the C-catalysts, suggest an increase in the extent of hydrogen bonding expected with the incorporation of chlorine into the support.

The difference in the catalytic behaviour of supported platinum and supported nickel may be

dependent on the metal assisted exchange. For nickel, the extent of the metal assisted exchange is substantially greater than that for platinum and appears to be dispersion dependent. This may very well account for the facile nature of catalytic hydrogenation over platinum in comparison to the demanding nature of the same reactions over nickel. Here, we have used the terms demanding and facile to denote dispersion sensitive and dispersion insensitive reactions, respectively.

In conclusion, we feel that although hydrogen atom spillover leading to high hydrogen atom concentrations on the support is unlikely, there is a distinct possibility that hydrogen atom enrichment at the metal support interface might possibly lead to enhanced catalytic activity. Our basis for these conclusions are (i) relatively low levels of hydrogen atom adsorption on the support oxides and (ii) a dispersion-dependent metal assisted deuterium-hydroxyl exchange in the case of supported nickel.

It might be appropriate to speculate why there appears to be a difference between the metal-catalysed exchange reactions of supported nickel and platinum. One very distinct possibility is that nickel tends to interact with alumina and silica to form aluminates and silicates more readily than platinum. It is for this reason that nickel is considerably harder to reduce than platinum. These metal-support interactions might possibly lower the activation energy for exchange, leading to a higher activity for deuterium-hydroxyl exchange.

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